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INCLUSION AND EQUITY: A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO HUMANIZED CARE FOR DEAF PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

It is known that one of the fundamental principles that brings dignity to human beings is communication. Through communication it is possible to guarantee rights, interaction and enable effective care. Communication becomes effective for deaf patients when the Brazilian Sign Language (Libras) is used. In this way, it is possible to ensure greater patient confidence in diagnoses and treatments, as well as promoting a holistic approach with equity and humanization in care.